

Review

Rhinoplasty in Asian Versus non-Asians Population: A Review

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Abstract: Rhinoplasty is an expanding topic in the field of plastic and cosmetic surgery. Interest is ongoing and developments have been rapid. Although several studies concentrated on Asian and non-Asian (American, Hispanic, Middle East etc) nose separately, but to our knowledge there is no study comparing the rhinoplasty surgical techniques used in Asian and non-Asian populations especially Americans (including Hispanic). It is a well-recognized fact that there is a distinctive quality to Asian rhinoplasty when compared with rhinoplasty for patients from other regions. For Asian patients, especially from East and Southeast Asia, the relatively smaller sized noses have made simple augmentation of the nose using alloplastic implant stand in for the term "Rhinoplasty." However Asian patients like higher noses and small nose tip. The purpose of this study was to analyze and categorize rhinoplasty in Asians and non-Asians, and then determine common surgical techniques that have general application to this particular population of patients.

Keywords: Rhinoplasty, Rhinoplasty in Asian, Rhinoplasty in Western, Rhinoplasty techniques, Rhinoplasty in Hispanic population

Introduction

East Asia has a population primarily of Malay descent. The noses are typically small

with voluminous thick skin, low dorsum, broad and hanging ala, retracted premaxilla, and bulbous tip [1-4]. The surgical techniques of rhinoplasty for these types of noses are distinct from the American/Western/Hispanic. The following are generally needed: dorsal augmentation, counter rotation and projection of the tip, and finally correction of hanging ala and alar flare/base. A number of non-Caucasian rhinoplasty recent studies have focused upon Asian or "Oriental" rhinoplasty [5-7]. Some have even referred to it as a "Mongoloid" rhinoplasty and few have focused on the Asian-American nose, which incorporates features representative of a variety of Asian countries, including China, Japan, Korea, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam. The purpose of this study was to analyze and categorize (if possible) the Asian-American nose, Hispanic nose and then determine common surgical techniques that have general application to this particular population of patients.

Materials and methods:

PubMed was searched in March 2020 attempting to find all articles describing Rhinoplasty in Asians and Non-Asians from April 1, 2003 to April, 2020. The Search terms used were "rhinoplasty in Asians" or "rhinoplasty in Caucasians" or "Rhinoplasty in Asian-Americans" or "Rhinoplasty". The reference lists of identified papers were searched for further leads. Two reviewers independently sorted through the search results and picked articles providing a detailed technical description of rhinoplasty procedures in different populations for further review. We excluded single case reports and non-English-language articles to facilitate the review process.

Common Surgical techniques used for Asian noses versus non-Asian noses :

There are certain anatomical features that seem to be common to most Indian noses (as compared with the Caucasian noses): greater pigmentation, thick skin, and weak cartilages. These characteristics have implications for the surgical techniques that are used in an Indian rhinoplasty.

Most Asian noses are characterized by thick skin with abundant subcutaneous fibrofatty tissue, a weak cartilaginous framework, short nasal bones, underdeveloped anterior nasal spine, and small quadrilateral septal cartilage. However, there are

individual variations. The associated cutaneous findings includes a wide and under projected dorsum, a low radix and nasion, a nasal tip that is bulbous, lacking definition, under projected, and either ptotic or over rotated (short nose); with a short columella and an alar base that is wide and flaring.

Silicone implant augmentation: It is the most widely per-PTFE sheets are usually thin compared with silicone implants, and might therefore be more useful for small augmenta-augmentation and tip projection improvement. Although a supratip break is sometimes requested, what western surgeons are familiar with, it is extremely discrete. When compared with another important difference with Caucasian patients is the almost universal request to have a full infratip lobule that needed to be carved into the proper shape. Larger augmentations require stacking of sheets. Gore-Tex (polytetrafluoroethylene; W.L. Gore & Asso-formed type of augmentation rhinoplasty in Asia and ciates, Flagstaff, AZ) is also popular, mostly in Korea. The popularity of silicone implants is multifactorial: cosmetics results are typically superior to autologous augmentation in Asians, implants are inexpensive, the procedure is simple, there is no donor-site morbidity, complications are relatively low, and it does not cut bridges for a salvage autologous rhinoplasty in case of complications. Thus, implant rhinoplasty is the first choice for Asian rhinoplasty. Autologous rhinoplasty indications are a patient requesting an autologous rhinoplasty, failed implant rhinoplasty, short nose, and correction of severe nasal deformity (such as congenital malformations and traumatic deformities).

Polytetrafluoroethylene Augmentation: Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE; Gore-Tex) has been widely used for dorsum and/or tip augmentation in stopped selling Gore-Tex implants for the plastic surgery in Koreas well as in China. There are no official alternative providers for the moment. Rhinoplasty techniques using PTFE for tip augmentation are often referred to as a "Korean-style rhinoplasty." PTEF typically comes in the form of sheets that need to be carved into the proper shape. PTEF sheets often thin contrast with silicon implants and might therefore be more useful for small augmentation. Larger augmentations may require stacking of sheets.

Silicon implant augmentation: Silicon implant augmentation is commonly considered to provide the best cosmetics results in Asians. There are several debates concerning

which shape of implant can achieve the best aesthetic/cosmetics results. There are two general shapes of nasal implants which are I-shaped and L-shaped. The dorsum is often supplemented by classic I-shaped implants. Surgeons who currently use them usually perform a concomitant tip-plasty to enhance tip projection. Some I-shaped implants also have a tip extension. Implants are placed subperiosteally on the nasal dorsum and act as cantilever grafts to augment the dorsum and support tip projection. However, these implants are relatively soft and are generally thought to provide less support for the tip than L-shaped implants as a columellar extension is absent. Cartilage grafting over the implant tip can also be used to provide more tip.

Autogenous augmentation: The use of diced cartilage in dorsal augmentation has been periodically documented in the literature as early as 1943 by Peer, in 1951 by Cottle, and in 1968 by Burian, though it did not gain wide-spread acceptance. Guerrerosantos revisited this concept and refining the technique by wrapping fragmented cartilage in fascia, while Erol brought a larger audience with his description of wrapping diced cartilage in Surgical in 2000. Modifications have been variously described, in the concept of using diced cartilage as the building block for dorsal augmentation, mainly adding assorted tissue adhesives to ease shaping of the graft, altering the material wrapping the cartilage, or fully foregoing an encasement. Diced cartilage with fascia represents a potentially ideal graft for dorsal augmentation, as it makes use of the lower complication rates associated with autologous grafts. It also provides a graft that has the ability to recreate dorsal aesthetic lines in a natural and predictable manner.

Rhinoplasty in Hispanic patients: (Hispanic: culture of Spain or of Portugal and, relating to, or being a person of Latin American descent living in the United States; especially: one of Cuban, Mexican, or Puerto Rican origin). A recent published study by the American Society of Plastic Surgeons (ASPS) in March 2008 reports a 15% increase in cosmetic surgery among ethnic patients. Compared with the ASPS data published in 2000, cosmetic surgery among Hispanics has increased by 173% with rhinoplasty among the top procedures requested. The 2007 ASPS national clearing house data on cosmetic demographics shows Hispanics as the second most popular group requesting cosmetic surgery with 1,011,071 patients; only behind Caucasians. It is imperative for plastic surgeons to become familiar with the Hispanic nose and its

different archetypes. Hispanic rhinoplasty is not a novel subject and Rollin, et al have previously described and classified the Hispanic nose.

Daniel classified the Hispanic nose into four major types: type I, Castilian; type II, Mexican American; type III, Mestizo; type IV, Creole. These three “archetypes” dictate the surgical techniques required for correction (rhinoplasty).

The Type I noses can often be corrected simply by dorsal reduction with minor tip and base modifications while Type II noses typically need dorsal augmentations with open rhinoplasty to address the tip using both suture techniques and tip grafts. The Type III noses have a significant vertical and horizontal disproportion. This requires correction with reduction of the wide nasal base in conjunction with dorsal augmentation and finally, an in-depth discussion regarding the patient's surgical goal is very important patient wants to obtain an aesthetically pleasing result while maintaining ethnicity or whether the patient wants to have a nose that appears like Caucasian.

Discussion :

With over 1.5 billion people and a long and complicated history South Asia is a diverse region. Over the past 50,000 years, a multitude of different cultural and ethnic groups have migrated and settled in the region. The earliest known inhabitants were those of the Indus Valley civilizations of Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro, which date as far back as 5000 Bce. Multiple waves of migrations from the Caucasus by Indo-European–speaking peoples, and violent invasions by the Persian and Central Asian Empire. Over the course of the centuries, this intermingling of peoples has contributed to a vast amount of morphologic diversity, and it is impossible to define a “typical” Asian nose. For example, many inhabitants of the northeastern Indian states have anatomical features and linguistic features in common with Southeast Asia, whilst the languages and morphologic features of northwestern India and Pakistan often have much in common with Persia or the Middle East [8-13. It should be noted that several authors have found differences in nasal morphology between North American Caucasians and Indians or South Asians [15]. For example, Patil et al. found that on average Indian women have greater nasal width, nasal length, and smaller nasolabial angle and tip projection. In addition, in our experience, there are certain common features of the Indian nose that differentiate it from the Caucasian nose: thicker skin, darker pigmentation, and weaker

upper and lower lateral cartilages [16, 17]. Patient satisfaction and improved quality of work is the primary goal of rhinoplastic treatment.

Rhinoplasty for Asian noses is significantly different from that for white noses. As rhinoplasty becomes increasingly popular among Asian people, it is important that the rhinoplasty surgeons master relevant anatomy and become skilled in necessary techniques to serve this segment of the population. A study of the Asian-American nose shows that while we have preferred to categorize the Asian-American nose (which is difficult because of variation within Asian national groups as well as within each group), Asian-American rhinoplasty is a procedure that involves vertical increase and, sometimes, large decrease.

In white and Asian population, there are similarities and differences between rhinoplasties. In comparison to rhinoplasty for white people, dorsal augmentation using alloplastic implants is more commonly done in Asian rhinoplasty. In the rhinoplastic surgeon's armamentarium shield grafting, multilayer cartilaginous tip grafting, modified vertical dome division, and tip onlay grafting are invaluable for improvements of the Asian nasal tip. However, in Asian rhinoplasty the most complicated procedure involves the correction of deformed noses, as in rhinoplasty for white people. Careful study of both the nasal framework and facial anatomy is needed for deviated noses and convex dorsum. Management of the septum is of special importance. Short noses often needed careful consideration in that the appearance of the short nose, brought about by a disharmony of nasal features may be real or imagined. The condition of the skin-soft tissue envelope, particularly in revision cases, poses a challenge, especially in skin closure.

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Conflicts of Interest

There is no conflict to declare.

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